

Life, Culture, and Economy: A Comprehensive Study of the Sarāk Community in Karaya Village, Jamtara, Jharkhand

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Introduction

Jainism is one of the classical religions, cultures and sects that enriched India's wealth of diversity. According to historians and pundits, around 500 years before the birth of Christ, at the hands of the twenty-fourth *Tirthankara* Mahavīraswami, Jainism entered the Indian map as a protestant and reformist religion and sect. Although the origin of this religion occurs more than two and a half thousand years ago, the opinion of the followers of that religion and the estimation of some historians. Eastern and adjacent northern India has been identified as the origin of Jainism. Based on several archaeological and written evidences, it is also assumed that the early followers of this religion lived in North and East India, i.e. historical Magadha and Anga territories who were known as '*Srāvakas*'. These *Srāvakas* settled in ancient Bengal before the historical period and played an important role behind the initiation of metallurgical civilization in the region and became the main driving force of the economy of the place. This *Srāvaka* category is later mentioned and known as '*Sarāk*' in various sources. The *Sarāk* caste is present in the historic land area of West Bengal and adjacent Jharkhand i.e. Purulia and Bankura in West Bengal, in some parts of Burdwan, Birbhum, Medinipur and several villages in the districts of Bokaro, Dhanbad, Ranchi, Jamtara, Dumka etc. in Jharkhand; Some parts of Orissa are still inhabited today. *Kareya* is one such village inhabited by *Sarāk* caste belonging to Nala block of Jamtara district of Jharkhand. It belongs to Bindapathar police station. About 45 families live in the village. *Sarāk* residents with the titles of Rai, Mandal, Maji and Singh can be found in the village. The following report has been written based on the information obtained during the field survey in the said village on January 2, 2024.

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Objectives of the Research:

The field study was mainly carried out for the purpose of carrying out a research project funded by the Indian Council of Social Science Research (ICSSR), whose main target is the historical land area of West Bengal (which is now in some parts of Purulia, Bankura, Burdwan, Birbhum, and Medinipur belonging to the district) and to observe the socio-economic, cultural and various aspects of life of *Srāvaka* or *Sarāk*, the original Jain community living in the historical Singhbhum and Manbhum fields of adjacent Jharkhand, in the light of sociology. Therefore, in order to implement the project, a survey has been carried out in one of the *Sarāk* villages of Jharkhand, some of the objectives of which are,

First, to understand the economic diversity of *Sarāk* society in terms of livelihood and to review its comparative value with neighbouring ethnic groups.

Secondly, to discuss the socio-social context of the *Sarāk* community in the light of the data emerging from the survey of several important aspects related to daily *Sarāk* life, such as food habits and cooking, drainage system, houses and public transport system etc.

Thirdly, to highlight the aspects like public health system, toilets, drinking water etc. of the said village and provide it if there is any crisis.

Fourthly, in the context of public education, the signature of *Sarāk* society, to promote the flow of women's education as well as overall education.

Fifth, an informative reference to the religious and reform traditions of *Sarāk* society and its current form.

Economic Patterns:

Most of the *Sarāk* families in the village depend on agriculture for their livelihood. In this case, there is a tendency to cultivate by employing labourers instead of cultivating by oneself. Rice is mainly grown as a cash crop, as evidenced by the extensive paddy fields surrounding the village (Fig. 1). Adjacent to the *Sarāk* neighbourhood live the *Bauri* community, who are also largely economically dependent on paddy cultivation. It would probably not be an exaggeration to say that this cultivation is the occupation of *Sarāk* or other neighbouring nations. Although a large section of *Sarāks* have now largely distanced themselves from their profession. At present, due to various risks in agriculture such as water uncertainty, lack of rain, crop value, wages, etc., many *Sarāks* have moved away from agriculture and some of them

have moved out of the district or the state and are working in various private companies or factories. In this context the names of two sons Keshav Kumar Singh and Kishore Kumar Singh of Sukhendu Bikas Singh, both of whom live in Howrah, West Bengal, working in jute mills.

(Fig. 1. extensive paddy fields surrounding the Kareya village, Purulia)

Many educated youth of the village have migrated to other states in the hope of work. In this regard, the names of Dulalchandra Roy's thirty-nine-year-old Chennai-resident son Shekhar Roy, Alakaranjan Mandal's Hyderabad-resident elder son Arindam Mondal, an engineer by profession, are mentioned. There are also a couple of people working as priests in Jain temples in other states. Interviewed in this context, the two sons of Irabala Devi (60 years old), Sujoy Mondal and Sudeep Mondal, who are currently worshipers of a Jain temple in Chhattisgarh. Apart from this, *Sarāk* residents working in government work in the village are also visible. In this regard, the names of 70-year-old retired Vinod Bihari Singh, who used to work in the office of the West Bengal government, and his 65-year-old unmarried sister Dr Banani Sinha, a professor of Bengali by profession, should be mentioned. Apart from all these, the village also has a medicine store run by the *Sarāks* and a couple of small grocery stores.

Sarāk residents of Kareya village depend on multiple banks located at 'Nala' 12 km away for banking facility. Bank of India, State Bank of India, Jharkhand Rajya Bank etc. can be mentioned in this context. ATM service is also located in 'Nala'. At least one member of every *Sarāk* family has at least one banking account. But very few do regular banking transactions. In the context of banking comes the word of loan. The survey revealed that a small number of people have taken loans from the state government banks for agriculture, some of them have also repaid the loans. Many of the *Sarāk* community in the village also have life insurance.

Home, Household and Other:

Most of the houses in the village are either half-pucca or fully-pucca (brick-house), there are hardly any mud house. The number of two-storied houses (Figure no. 3) is also high, which mainly indicates the financial stability of the local *Sarāks*. Tin (Fig. 2) or tiles are used as roofs on half-timbered houses. Houses usually have two to three rooms, but in joint families the number is sometimes as high as 6-7. Except for one or two houses, every house in the village has a toilet. During the survey, it was found that many toilets have been constructed for the purpose of Central Project Grant. In the interview, everyone said that they use the toilet.

(Fig. 2 & 3. Two-storied Brick house and mud house in the Kareya village, Purulia)

Sarāk households in the village generally use coal as fuel, gas and wood are used to a lesser extent. In some completed houses, fuel gas is used for daily cooking, but in most houses, gas consumption is very limited. Each house has a separate space for cooking, in this case some houses have a separate kitchen and some houses have a small kitchen coexistence with the balcony. But generally the kitchen and gas oven for coal and wood heating are located in the balcony section (Fig. 4, 5).

(Fig. 4 & 5. coal and wood heating kitchen and gas oven kitchen in the Kareya village, Purulia)

Every single house in the village has electricity connection. However, when the issue of drinking water came up, many people expressed problems in the interview phase. A handful of houses (about 7-8) have underground tubewells, several old wells are also observed (Fig. 6),

(Fig. 6. old wells as drinking water resource in the Kareya village, Purulia)

although almost all of them have to rely on government taps located within 500 meters at one end of *Sarāk Mahalla* for drinking water. In fact, the problems of the water layer due to the rocky soil and the excess of minerals in the water are the reasons for the problem of drinking water, said several people of the village.

(Fig. 7 & 8. open and covered drainage system in the Kareya village, Purulia)

There is no public drainage system within the *Sarāk Para* of the village. In addition, many houses have water drainage systems, but it has gone into the cesspit. So, in that sense the drainage system is not visible. However, open and buried drains can be seen in several houses (Figures 7 and 8). On the whole, the drainage system of rural style is seen there.

Animal Husbandry:

Cows account for more than half of the livestock in *Sarāk* households. Cow's milk is considered as a marketed beverage in addition to being in their diet. Besides, cow dung is also

used for making fuel. The presence of goats is also visible in a few houses. Although many *Sarāk* households used to have oxen for agricultural purposes, they are no longer seen due to the difficulty of rearing them and the fact that the practical utility of oxen in agriculture has declined somewhat, although in the neighbourhood of the Bauri tribe, oxen, buffaloes and goats are also reared in addition to cows (Fig. 9).

(Fig. 9. A herd of cattle beside the Kareya village, Purulia)

Transport, its means-forms and problems:

Most of the houses in the village have both bicycles and motorbikes. Even some lower middle-class households can find motorbikes. As the reason for this, many interviewees were asked that since there is no decent and regular public transport system in the area yet, in that case own motorbike is the only option. It is good to say in this context that the roads or communication system in or around Kareya is not very good. The distance from the village to the nearest traffic road is about 3 to 4 km. Although traffic is very low due to public transport on the road, in this case reserved tempo or toto are relied upon to come from the local market area i.e. Nala Block sector to the village. This communication difficulty has become quite a barrier in terms of education and employment among the local *Sarāk* community.

Different aspects of education:

The primary school is located within the village. The high school is situated at a distance of 8 kilometres in Machladihi, serving as the sole educational institution for the majority of *Sarāk* pupils in the area. The nearest college is 12 km away at Nala, and the university is Sidho Kanu University at Dumka, about 60-65 km away. In spite of this obstacle of distance to educational institutions, the number of educated *Sarāk* youth is not less. There are many boys with BA, BSc, many have completed industrial training. A few engineering (B.Tech.) students

are also among the village *Sarāk* society. However, girls do not exhibit a significant inclination towards pursuing higher education. One example is Dr. Banani Sinha, who holds a degree in Bengali language and literature. She grew up in a rural area and has dedicated her career to teaching, which is now coming to an end. In addition, a female school instructor was hired, although it was not possible to meet her owing to time limitations. Currently, both young and senior *Sarāk* youth have a certain reluctance towards pursuing higher education. This is mostly owing to the high availability of enrolment opportunities and the lack of economic prospects inside the state. A significant number of young individuals are employed in private enterprises abroad without securing employment opportunities after completing their education. Additionally, the *Sarāk* community in Jharkhand is facing exclusion from the state's administrative register, resulting in a lack of valid official identification cards. Simultaneously, despite their status as a minority population, the *Sarāk* community harbours suppressed feelings of bitterness and anger due to the lack of access to numerous possibilities. This sentiment was evident in the interviews conducted as part of the survey.

Public health, medical infrastructure and initiatives

Due to time constraints, a comprehensive survey of all families in the village was not feasible. However, among the families that were surveyed, it was found that 45 percent of them have at least one chronic disease, such as diabetes or hypertension. Consequently, conventional medication is utilised in all of those households. Gas-heartburn is a common occurrence in most families, although it has not become a chronic condition. In addition to these factors, numerous families have various age-related ailments such as respiratory infections and musculoskeletal disorders. Nevertheless, a significant number of individuals have yet to achieve a drug-free status despite their diligent efforts and the influence of the contemporary lifestyle. Within the village, there exists a pharmacy managed by a *Sarāk* individual. This establishment serves as a sanctuary for both the *Sarāk* community and those from other castes during times of adversity. In addition, there is a practitioner of homeopathy named Alokranjan Mandal. In addition to the villagers, individuals from nearby villages who have faith in homeopathic treatment also seek his services. There is no authorised medical facility located within the village. The closest government health centre is located approximately 7-8 kilometres away at Bindapathar. The prominent government medical facility in the area is Nalay, located approximately 12 kilometres away. Additionally, there is the Jamtara Zilla Sadar Hospital, situated at a distance of 26-28 km. Furthermore, there are various nursing homes in close proximity. Despite the relatively short distance, the inadequate road infrastructure and

public transportation system pose a significant hurdle to emergency treatment. Numerous local residents have voiced their discontent. Maternal health and child health are inherently interconnected with the health system. According to the survey data, it is evident that pregnant women currently choose to give birth at Jamtara Hospital or, in some cases, at private nursing homes, following modern medical practices. Many women reported that the traditional practice of giving birth at home has been abandoned in this area for approximately twenty to twenty-five years. The Government of Jharkhand fulfils many obligations in ensuring the well-being of mothers and children by offering immunisation, promoting physical fitness, and providing growth-enhancing medications, among other measures.

Sociology: Division, Marriage and Feminism

The *Sarāk* community in the nearby area is generally cohesive. Marriage typically involves forming a connection with the *Sarāk* family, although there are also instances of unconventional marital unions observed in contemporary times. Multiple *Sarāk* individuals said that there used to be a customary practice of marriage within the *Sarāk* community, but it is no longer present in contemporary times. In previous eras, there was a prevailing inclination to arrange marriages for daughters at a tender age, a practice that is no longer perceived in the same manner. The marriage customs of the indigenous *Sarāks* adhere to customary and widely practiced traditions, without any distinct customs observed.

Diet

The survey phase of asking the housewives and others from numerous *Sarāk* houses revealed that a few families and some older individuals who are not aware with the tradition of Jan *Sarāk* community adhere to a vegetarian diet. The majority of the remaining individuals consume non-vegetarian meals. In the Bengali-speaking *Sarāk* family of Karaya, rice with vegetable curry and dal is widely regarded as the primary meal, consumed in the afternoon, while bread is commonly eaten at night. Their diet consists of a diverse range of seasonal vegetables (Figure No. 10), various types of legumes, cow's milk, fish, eggs, meat, and other foods.

(Fig. 10: Winter vegetables kept for cooking by a family of Karaya village; It should be noted here that radish is prohibited in the Sarāk diet, just like other subterranean items.)

Many individuals have stated that they consume non-vegetarian cuisine when dining out, although adhering to a vegetarian diet at home. According to multiple *Sarāk* individuals, the absence of a Jain temple in this area renders any form of religious practice ineffective.

Religion, Reforms and Rituals

The *Sarāk* people residing in Karaya village are members of the Adideva clan, whilst two out of four families belong to the Rishideva clan. Despite being fully cognisant of their authentic tribe and religious affiliation, hardly anyone practices Swadharmacharan. Located in the village of Bindapathar, there is a Jain temple where the Jain religious royal family hosts numerous Jain religious festivities. Residents of this village also actively engage in these events. The incidents of Parusana, Oli, etc. are explicitly identified as specific occurrences. Nevertheless, some individuals have reported that they did not receive an invitation or phone contact during the previous year. According to an anonymous individual from the *Sarāk* community, they have no incentive to convert since they do not receive any religious or other benefits from the Jain organisation. The village previously had a Jain Pathshala, overseen by Saikat Singh, but it is no longer operational. The majority of the *Sarāk* family members residing in the village travelled to Madhuban and paid a visit to Parshnath. However, the number of visitors to Parshanath in recent years is very low. Nevertheless, the *Sarāks* in villages predominantly adhere to Hindu religious customs. Vinodbihari Sinha, whose family resides in *Sarāk* Para of Durga Mandir, is the subject of discussion in this case. Every year, Durga Puja and Kali Puja are celebrated at this location. He mentioned that sacrifice is also performed at Kali Puja. In addition, Charak Puja is also performed on Charak Sankranti. To put it simply, it may be stated that his family has just become deeply involved in Hindu Shaktism following a significant period of religious engagement. The ubiquity of tulsi mancha in every household of

Echara village, together with the adornment of tulusi garlands by several individuals, unequivocally signifies the prevalence of Vaishnava religious observance in the area.

Conclusion

The objective of this research paper is not to reveal any basic aspects, but rather to offer a full diary of the current flow of the society, economy, and culture of the traditional Sarāk community in the form of sociology. This is the conclusion that can be drawn from the research study. In the event that the current work contributes, either directly or indirectly, to the growth of the aforementioned nation and society at some point in the future, the author will consider his efforts to be partially beneficial.

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